

MediLabSecure One Health Situation Analysis in Bosnia and Herzegovina

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

- AMR: Antimicrobial Resistance
- BiH: Bosnia and Herzegovina
- BOHN: Balkan One Health Network
- ECDC: European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
- EU: European Union
- FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
- FBiH: The Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina
- G20: The Group of Twenty
- HIFRS: Health Insurance Fund of Republic of Srpska
- ISS: Italian National Institute of Health (Istituto Superiore di Sanità)
- IPH FBiH: Institute of Public Health of Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina
- IPH RS: Institute of Public Health of Republic of Srpska
- MoCA: Ministry of Civil Affairs
- MoFTER: Ministry of Foreign Trade and Economic Relations of Bosnia and Herzegovina
- MoHSW: Ministry of Health and Social Welfare
- NGS: Next Generation Sequencing
- OHHLEP: One Health High-Level Expert Panel
- OH: One Health
- OHCF: One Health Conceptual Framework
- OH JPA: One Health Joint Plan of Action (2022–2026)
- OHMeSA: One Health MediLabSecure Situation Analysis
- PH Group: Public Health Working Group
- PHI: Public Health Institute
- PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction
- RS: The Republic of Srpska
- UN: United Nations
- UNDP: United Nations Development Programme
- UNECE: United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
- UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme
- UNSA-VF: University of Sarajevo - Veterinary Faculty
- VBDs: Vector-Borne Diseases
- VObiH: Veterinary Office of Bosnia and Herzegovina
- VIS: Veterinary Information System of Republic of Srpska
- WHO: World Health Organization
- WOAH: World Organisation for Animal Health (formerly OIE)

1 INTRODUCTION

The past five decades have seen an unprecedented emergence of epidemic arboviral diseases, a type of vector-borne diseases (VBDs) caused by viruses transmitted to people by bites of infected arthropods [1]. The [MediLabSecure](#) (MLS) project is a European project that aims at preventing risks associated to arbovirus infections within 22 countries across the Balkan and Black Sea, Maghreb and Sahel, and Middle-East regions (Figure 1), by strengthening a structured, inclusive and institutionalized One Health (OH) approach. The project's overarching goal aims to enhance networking activities and capacity building, thereby improving integrated surveillance and control of emerging arboviruses and VBDs. This involves strengthening cross-border collaborations and improving prevention and preparedness capacities and capabilities of the OH workforce. The Public Health working group (PH Group) of the MLS project led by the Italian National Institute of Health (Istituto Superiore di Sanità – ISS) conducted the OH MediLabSecure Situation Analysis (OHMeSA) in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) in collaboration with the experts of the relevant institutions in BiH. The goal of the OHMeSA study was to identify strengths, areas for improvement and opportunities to strengthening the OH system for prevention and preparedness to arboviruses and other VBDs and zoonoses in BiH. The aim of this report is to provide information on the OHMeSA study in BiH, its methodology and its results.

Figure 1: Countries involved in [MLS Network](#)

2 BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

The international and scientific community has been calling since many years to strengthen prevention and preparedness to VBDs and zoonotic diseases by integrating a systemic approach, such as the OH approach [2,3]. The recently established One Health High Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP) defined the OH approach as an integrated, unifying approach that aims to achieve optimal and sustainable health outcomes for people, animals, plants and the environment by mobilizing multiple sectors, disciplines and communities [4]. However, operationalization and implementation of the OH approach are challenging [5]. The Quadripartite Organizations – the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH, founded as OIE), and the World Health Organization (WHO), responding to international requests to prevent future pandemics and to promote health sustainably through the OH approach, have developed the OH Joint Plan of Action (2022–2026) (OH JPA) to collectively advocate and support the operationalization and implementation of OH [6].

Within the framework of the MLS project and with the support of institutions in BiH, the OHMeSA study was promoted to foster the development of the OH approach in BiH and to promote its operationalization and implementation.

3 THE ONE HEALTH MEDILABSECURE SITUATION ANALYSIS STUDY IN BOSNIA & HERZEGOVINA

3.1 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The One Health MediLabSecure Situation Analysis (OHMeSA) study is an action-oriented situation analysis aimed at strengthening the OH system in BiH by assessing the level of integration among different sectors and stakeholders for the prevention and preparedness to threats at the human-animal-environment interface, such as vector-borne diseases and zoonoses.

The specific objectives are:

- ✓ Describe sectors and stakeholders engaged in the OH system in BiH.
- ✓ Identify priority health threats that could benefit from the OH approach. Use the prioritized health threats as case studies to assess the integration of OH approaches in prevention and preparedness strategies.
- ✓ Enhance awareness of the stakeholders about the importance of multisectoral and multidisciplinary collaboration to face emerging threats.
- ✓ Identify opportunities to enhance the OH system and the integrated surveillance and early warning systems of the prioritised pathogens.
- ✓ Promote comprehensive capacity building for all stakeholders involved in the study.

3.2 THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The situation analysis was guided by the One Health Conceptual Framework (OHCF) [7], elaborated in the context of The Group of Twenty (G20) 2021 Meeting. The OHCF aims at strengthening OH national systems by highlighting gaps in existing prevention, preparedness and response strategies and by identifying in country procedures that allow integration of OH approaches. The framework identifies five country targets areas and related priority actions which should be considered to ensure OH approach operationalisation and implementation at country level by addressing governance mechanisms, prevention and preparedness strategies, data collection systems, capacity building activities and evaluation strategies. The framework identifies also two international targets with priority actions aimed at guiding the development of national OH strategies on the basis of harmonised OH global strategies to enhance cross-border collaborations and capacity building initiatives (Figure 2).

For the scope of this study the OHCF was used to guide the situation analysis and to develop a checklist to collect information during the consultation with the stakeholders.

The ONE HEALTH CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The present framework aims at guiding the relevant national sectors to strengthen the One Health system and implement harmonised and context-driven One Health strategies to support health security globally.

Target areas

National level

International level

GOVERNANCE

PREVENTION AND PREPAREDNESS

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

CAPACITY BUILDING

CONSOLIDATION AND EVALUATION OF THE SYSTEM IN PLACE

HARMONISATION OF PLANS AND CROSS BORDER COLLABORATIONS

HARMONISED CAPACITY BUILDING

Priorities for Action

Establishing a national multisectoral and multistakeholder team to set principles, rules and procedures to allow operationalisation of OH strategies.

Assessing the opportunity and benefits of setting up a OH National Center

Enacting laws and identifying resources for OH operationalisation

Connecting OH strategies to prevention and preparedness plans by establishing a multisectoral team (OH Team) in charge for development, implementation and monitoring of plans

Develop inclusive strategies engaging all the actors, including communities

Identification of national priority areas to be monitored and related monitoring indicators/metrics

Verifying available sources of information and data

Development of integrated and interoperable database connected with early warning and surveillance systems

Development of training curricula about OH prevention and preparedness

Training of the OH workforce included in national plans

Piloting OH strategies and exercising about their implementation

Identifying monitoring and impact indicators

Assessing level of implementation of OH indications in prevention and pandemic plans

Assessing added value of OH in prevention and preparedness

Developing and updating international guidance and regulations to integrate OH strategies in prevention and preparedness plans and international early warning systems

Identification of OH preparedness indicators/metrics in collaboration with National OH Teams

Establishing Quadripartite collaborating Centers at National OH Centers

Facilitating Networking opportunities between OH National Centers

Integration of OH principles in international trainings and in capacity assessment tools

Promoting harmonised and multicounty exercises

Figure 2: the OHCF [7]

3.3 STUDY DESIGN

The OHMeSA study was guided by a team of researchers from the ISS and performed with the support of stakeholders from BiH institutions and organizations.

The study adopted a mixed-methods approach including a desk research and interviews to stakeholders during a visit to BiH (Figure 3).

The methodology of this study is based on protocols developed in previous OHMeSA studies, including applications in Armenia and Montenegro [8,9].

Figure 3: The methodological phases of the Study

Preparation and Desk Research

This phase involved initial contacts and information exchange with the relevant institutions. A stakeholder mapping process was carried out, followed by the collection of necessary documentation and the development of the study protocol. Additionally, desk research was conducted to gather information on the OH system and OH threats specific to BiH, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the local context and challenges.

Prioritization exercise

An online prioritization exercise was planned to identify the key health threats at the human-animal-environment interface in BiH. The exercise focused on zoonotic and arboviral diseases that pose significant risks to human, animal, and environmental health. The pathogens considered in this exercise included West Nile Virus (WNV), Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever (CCHF), Avian Influenza, Trichinellosis, Brucella, Leptospirosis, and Anthrax, selected for their known impacts on public health, animal populations, and the environment.

To ensure a structured and transparent prioritization process, the criteria for ranking these pathogens were developed based on protocols from previous studies conducted in Armenia and Montenegro [8,9], as well as the CDC’s [10] established guidelines for OH prioritization exercises. The exercise was facilitated through the interactive polling platform [Mentimeter™](#), allowing stakeholders to rank each pathogen according to factors such as frequency of occurrence, impact, and preparedness needs with consideration of its OH significance. This interactive process enabled experts to assess each pathogen’s potential threat in a collaborative and transparent manner.

Indicators for OH threats prioritization
Threat detected or caused outbreaks /epidemics in the past ten years
Threat detected in a new location or population in the country or neighboring countries in the past ten years
Threat whose animal host (domestic or wild) is/are in close proximity to humans
Threat whose related vector/s' presence and abundancy are increasing due to anthropogenic, climatic, and environmental factors
Threat affecting food safety and /or food security
Threat impacting greatly socio-economic aspects in case of outbreak
Threat benefitting the most from the integration of OH in preparedness/surveillance/response
Threat for whom a OH preparedness /surveillance plan is available
Threat benefitting the most from the integration of environmental and climatic data in its / their surveillance
Threat which has activated a recent response action to contain a potential outbreak of the disease
Threat with an integrated data collection and analysis system
Threat that would benefit from cross-border collaboration for effective surveillance and response within BiH entities

Table 1: Indicators for OH threats prioritization.

Site Visit

To conduct meetings and consultations during the site visit, the team developed comprehensive checklists based on the OHCF. These checklists were essential in guiding the situation analysis of the country's OH systems and the coordination across different sectors (Annex I, II, and III).

Key areas assessed included:

- Governance
- Prevention and Preparedness
- Data collection and analysis
- Capacity Building
- Consolidation and Evaluation of the system in place
- Harmonization of plans and cross border collaboration
- Harmonised Capacity building

This methodical approach provided a clear picture of BiH's OH strategies, highlighting strengths, gaps, and opportunities for improvement.

The site visit to BiH was conducted from 14 to 19 October 2024 by the ISS team.

The aim of the mission was to examine the country's preparedness and strategies for preventing, detecting, and responding to health threats, particularly those that arise at the intersection of human, animal, and environmental health. The team visited key institutions in both Sarajevo and Banja Luka, engaging with health authorities, public health experts, and veterinary health professionals to understand the country's OH approach. Additionally, an online meeting was conducted with a

representative from Brčko District and with UNEP to explore regional health initiatives and collaborations.

4 RESULTS

4.1 PREPARATION AND DESK RESEARCH

Based on the desk review, a country portfolio was designed and shared with relevant stakeholders for input, ensuring that the portfolio reflected the key issues and priorities identified during the research phase (see Annex IV-Country Portfolio). The main outcomes of the country portfolio are reported from paragraphs 4.4

4.2 INSTITUTIONS INVOLVEMENT AND STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING

Institution/organisation	Invited to take part in the study and kept informed	Interviewed
Ministry of Civil Affairs of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Department of Health)	✓	✓
Ministry of Foreign Trade and Economic Relations of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Veterinary Services)	✓	
Food Safety Agency of Bosnia and Herzegovina	✓	
Veterinary Office of Bosnia and Herzegovina	✓	
Public Health Institute of Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina	✓	✓
Clinical Center University of Sarajevo, Unit for clinical microbiology	✓	✓
University of Sarajevo - Veterinary Faculty (UNSA-VF)	✓	✓
Institute for Health and Food Safety Zenica	✓	✓
Ministry of Health and Social Welfare of the Republic of Srpska	✓	✓
Public Health Institute of Republic of Srpska	✓	✓
Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Srpska	✓	✓
Public Institution Veterinary Institute of the Republic of Srpska "Dr. Vaso Butozan" Banja Luka	✓	✓
Department for Health and Other Services, Government of Brčko district of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Sub-Department for Public Health)	✓	✓
FAO- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations	✓	
World Health Organization, WHO - Country Office for Bosnia and Herzegovina	✓	✓
United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)	✓	✓

Table 2: List of Institutions who took part in the Study

4.3 PRIORITIZATION EXERCISE

The experts identified with the stakeholders mapping were invited to take part in the on-line prioritization exercise, which was conducted on September 13, 2024 aimed to identify key pathogens of concern at the human-animal-environment interface, focusing on both arboviral and zoonotic diseases. Six participants took part in the prioritisation representing the Ministry of Civil Affairs (MoCA) of BiH (Department of Health), Public Health Institute of RS, Food Safety Agency, Public Health Institute PHI of FBiH, Institute for Health and Food Safety Zenica, Department of Health and Other Services of Brčko District of BiH (Sub-Department for Public Health). They were asked to assess the significance of various pathogens, including WNV, CCHFV, Brucella, Avian Influenza, Leptospirosis, Trichinellosis, and Anthrax, based on their public health impact, relevance to OH approaches, and the need for surveillance and response efforts.

WNV received 24 votes across the 12 indicators, making it the highest-priority arbovirus. CCHFV was mentioned 9 times, indicating its recognition as an important concern. Among zoonotic pathogens, Brucella was the most frequently mentioned, with 26 votes, followed by Avian Influenza with 22 votes. Leptospirosis and Trichinellosis each received 16 votes, while Anthrax was mentioned 10 times (Figures 4 and 5). As a result, WNV and Brucella were identified as key pathogens to be used as case studies to discuss integration of sectors in the related surveillance system and PPR measure during the site visit.

Figure 4: Results of the arbovirus Prioritization Exercise

Figure 5: Results of the Other Pathogen Prioritization Exercise

4.4 BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

BiH is a country located in South-eastern Europe, in the Balkan Peninsula. It shares borders with Croatia to the north, south, and west, Serbia to the east, and Montenegro to the southeast.

BiH consists of two entities:

1. The FBiH, which occupies around 51% of the country, primarily in the western and central regions.
2. The RS, which comprises about 49% of the country and is located in the north and east.

Moreover, Brčko District of BiH was established as a territorial condominium after the 2000 arbitration decision, with joint ownership by both entities. It is an administrative unit with its own administration, but BiH institutions have sovereignty over it [11]. Sarajevo is the capital of BiH and the largest city, while Banja Luka is the administrative center of RS.

BiH has a complex governance system, which includes the BiH Council of Ministers at the country level, the Governments of FBiH and RS at the entity levels, and the Government of Brčko District of BiH. FBiH is further divided into 10 cantons, each with its own regional administration, laws, and municipal divisions [12].

According to the latest census of 2013, BiH had a population of slightly over 3.5 million, a number that is declining, with a projected population of approximately 3.25 million by 2020 [13].

Considering that health is the responsibility of the Entities as well as Brčko District, there are:

- The Ministry of Health (MoH) of the FBiH
- The Ministry of Health and Social Welfare (MoHSW) of RS and
- Department of Health and Other Services of Brčko District of BiH

According to the Article 15 of Law on Ministries and Other Administrative Bodies of BiH, the MoCA is responsible for carrying out tasks and duties which are within the competence of BiH and relate to defining basic principles, coordinating activities and harmonizing plans of the Entity authorities and defining a strategy at the international level, among other, in the field of health.

4.5 FEDERATION OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

The FBiH is one of the two entities of BiH, representing about 51% of the country's territory and population. It consists of ten cantons, each with its own government and legislature. The Federation manages key sectors such as health, education, and social welfare, with these responsibilities often shared with the cantons.

Health System in the FBiH

The FBiH operates a decentralized health system, with healthcare services primarily managed at the cantonal level. Each of FBiH's ten cantons has its own MoH, responsible for overseeing healthcare delivery within its jurisdiction. The Federal MoH plays a coordinating role, facilitating the implementation of national public health policies but with limited authority over direct service delivery. This decentralized structure can lead to inconsistencies in healthcare management and delivery across cantons [14].

Healthcare financing in FBiH is also decentralized, with mandatory health insurance contributions being the primary source of funding. Each canton manages its own health insurance system, ensuring coordination and uniform coverage across the region, though significant disparities in service provision and resources exist between cantons. For instance, Sarajevo Canton offers nearly universal coverage, while other cantons, such as Herzegovina-Neretva, have lower coverage rates [15,16].

FBiH's health services are provided through a network of public healthcare facilities that offer primary, secondary, and tertiary care. Primary healthcare is primarily delivered through family medicine centers, while secondary and tertiary services are provided by hospitals and Clinical centers with Clinical Center University of Sarajevo as the largest tertiary-level institution, including the Clinical Center of Sarajevo. Despite this system, out-of-pocket expenses remain a significant barrier for many citizens, particularly in rural areas, where resources are unevenly distributed [17].

As of 2020, the overall health insurance coverage rate in FBiH was 87%, with children under 18 entitled to full healthcare benefits, regardless of insurance status. Uninsured adults have access to essential services, including emergency care, pregnancy-related care, and treatment for chronic conditions [13].

Veterinary Sector in FBiH

The veterinary sector in FBiH is regulated by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Water Management and Forestry, which oversees animal diseases, food safety, and veterinary medicine in compliance with EU standards. The ministry plays a crucial role in disease surveillance and reporting, particularly for zoonotic diseases.

Veterinary services are decentralized, with each canton having its own veterinary authority. These cantonal authorities are responsible for implementing animal health programs within their jurisdiction. The cantonal authorities collaborate with the central government on disease surveillance, inspections, and food safety [18,19].

Key Contribution of the Veterinary Institute UNSA during the COVID-19 Pandemic

An illustrative example of intersectoral collaboration within the veterinary sector in FBiH is the active role of the Veterinary Institute of the University of Sarajevo (VI UNSA-VF) during the COVID-19 pandemic. This case highlights the effective implementation of the One Health approach and the strong coordination between the Federal Ministry of Health (FMZ) and UNSA-VF.

The UNSA-VF was designated by FMZ as an authorized laboratory for SARS-CoV-2 diagnostics and led genomic sequencing efforts, contributing to:

- The largest number of whole-genome SARS-CoV-2 sequences deposited from Bosnia and Herzegovina into the GISAID database (more than 1250 whole genomes).
- Advanced molecular surveillance, which enabled better tracking of SARS-CoV-2 variants in the country.
- Interdisciplinary cooperation between veterinary and human health sectors, reinforcing the importance of cross-sectoral collaboration in pandemic preparedness and response.

Such intersectoral engagement highlights the capacity of the veterinary sector in FBiH to contribute meaningfully to public health efforts and demonstrates the practical implementation of One Health principles through effective collaboration across sectors.

Environmental Health

The Federal Ministry of Environment and Tourism is responsible for environmental protection in FBiH. The Federation has implemented several initiatives, including the Air Quality Improvement

Project approved by the World Bank [20]. FBiH is also part of the EU’s Green Agenda for the Western Balkans, focusing on environmental protection and sustainable development [21].

Additionally, UNDP signed an agreement with the Federation in 2024 to further support environmental sustainability [22].

Site visit and Consultations

Table 3. Overview of the consulted Institutions and their Roles

Institution	Role and Responsibilities	Dates of Meetings
Ministry of Civil Affairs of BiH (Department of Health)	Responsible for carrying out tasks and duties which are within the competence of BiH and relate to defining basic principles, coordinating activities and harmonizing plans of the Entity authorities and defining a strategy at the international level, among other, in the field of health.	15 October 2024
Public Health Institute of the FBiH	Monitors public health, conducts epidemiological surveillance, implements health promotion programs, and supports the development of health policies in the Federation. Ensures public health safety across cantons.	15 October 2024
World Health Organization (WHO) - Country Office for BiH	Supports BiH in strengthening healthcare, improving public health, and addressing health challenges. Collaborates with local and international partners to implement health policies aligned with WHO standards.	15 October 2024
Clinical Center University of Sarajevo, Unit for Clinical Microbiology	A leading medical laboratory specializing in diagnostic microbiology. Provides services for diagnosing infectious diseases, conducting research, and supporting healthcare institutions.	16 October 2024
University of Sarajevo - Veterinary Faculty (UNSA-VF)	BiH’s institution for veterinary education and research. Offers EU-accredited programs, focuses on OH principles, and contributes to animal health, food safety, and public health.	16 October 2024

Ministry of Civil Affairs (MoCA) of BiH

The first day of the site visit began with a meeting at the MoCA of BiH. The discussion centred on the government's health policies, with particular attention paid to strategies for addressing emerging health threats through multi-sectoral collaboration. The meeting provided valuable insight into the ministry's role in coordinating health initiatives across different sectors.

WHO Country Office for BiH

Later in the day, the team met with representatives from the WHO Country Office for BiH. The discussion focused on the WHO's efforts to support BiH's health system, particularly in strengthening capacities for responding to global health threats through the OH approach. The meeting highlighted the challenges of integrating the human health and veterinary sectors, which currently have limited collaboration, especially in terms of data access and communication channels. WHO has been promoting initiatives to enhance OH collaboration in BiH, with a particular focus on AMR as a common agenda to drive intersectoral cooperation. The country is exploring a national quadripartite coordination framework involving human health, animal health, agriculture, and the environment.

Federation-Level Institutions

Public Health Institute of the Federation of BiH

The team visited the PHI of the FBiH, where the institute's work on public health surveillance and disease prevention was discussed. The conversation focused on the Institute's efforts to monitor infectious diseases, with particular emphasis on zoonotic diseases and their potential to impact public health. The team also explored the institute's data collection and reporting systems, including how they collaborate with veterinary and environmental sectors to enhance surveillance capabilities. Challenges related to resource constraints, data integration, and cross-sector collaboration were also addressed, highlighting the need for a more unified approach in managing emerging health threats.

Clinical Center University of Sarajevo – Unit for Clinical Microbiology

The next day, the team visited the Laboratory for Clinical Microbiology at the Clinical Center University of Sarajevo, the largest hospital in BiH. This laboratory plays a vital role in diagnostic services for both inpatients and outpatients, conducting over 200,000 analyses annually. During the visit, the team gained valuable insights into the country's diagnostic capabilities, particularly in relation to infectious diseases. The laboratory's involvement in pathogen surveillance was discussed, with a

focus on its work with arboviruses such as WNV, and its ongoing efforts to enhance diagnostic technologies, including Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) and Next Generation Sequencing (NGS). The laboratory also plays a crucial role in the country's influenza surveillance and is working towards becoming the officially designated National Influenza Center, supported by the WHO. Despite facing challenges, including limited intersectoral coordination and human resource shortages, the laboratory continues to improve its capacity. It serves as WHO referral laboratory for measles and rubella and functional referral laboratory for AMR and contributes to broader regional health security efforts. The discussions also emphasized the need for enhanced collaboration across sectors, particularly between human health, animal health, and environmental health, to strengthen disease monitoring and response capabilities.

University of Sarajevo - Veterinary Faculty (UNSA-VF)

The day was concluded with a meeting with a representative from the University of Sarajevo - Veterinary Faculty (UNSA-VF) where the team gained an overview of the veterinary sector's contributions to the OH strategy. The discussion highlighted the challenges in integrating OH in BiH, particularly due to the country's complex political and administrative structure. Despite efforts to collaborate, significant barriers persist, such as the lack of coordinated data-sharing between human health and veterinary sectors. The conversation also focused on the role of the Veterinary Institute Sarajevo as the national reference laboratory for influenza and Newcastle disease, as well as its involvement in surveillance efforts for zoonotic diseases like Brucella and WNV. The laboratory's role in improving diagnostic tools and fostering cross-sector collaboration was discussed, along with ongoing challenges in coordinating surveillance activities across different regions.

In accordance with the FBiH Veterinary Law ('Official Gazette of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina,' no. 46/2000, 76/2016, and 90/2023), the University of Sarajevo - Veterinary Faculty officially performs the duties of the Veterinary Institute of the FBiH until its formal establishment."

Analysis of the findings

One Health System Description

It was observed that the health system in the FBiH operates under a decentralized structure, with health services managed primarily at the cantonal level. Each canton has its own health authority overseeing healthcare delivery within its jurisdiction. The MoCA plays a central role in coordinating national health initiatives. This decentralized structure allows local adaptation of healthcare policies, while the ministry ensures alignment with broader public health goals.

Additionally, the Infectious Disease Committees (IDCs) in FBiH play a key role in coordinating responses to infectious disease outbreaks and facilitating cross-sector collaboration. These committees are integral to aligning the efforts of human, animal, and environmental health sectors, especially within the One Health framework. However, decentralized governance still requires greater coordination efforts between cantonal ministries, the national health bodies, and the IDCs to ensure effective collaboration across sectors and institutions. A lack of formal communication mechanisms further limits cross-sector collaboration, affecting the integration of human, animal, and environmental health data. Data collected by cantonal public health institutes is aggregated by the IPH of the FBiH, which consolidates the data and reports it to MoCA. From there, the data is shared with international organizations like the WHO and the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), enabling effective national and international collaboration on public health matters.

Table 4. System analysis based on the OHCF Pillars

Pillar	Strengths	Areas for Improvement	Opportunities
Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active participation in Networks such as MLS and BOHN enhance cross-sector collaboration. • Collaboration with international organization, like WHO, UNEP and ECDC, strengthens public health policies. <p>An Infectious Disease Committee at federal level, representing both public health and veterinary sectors, fostering enhanced coordination across health sectors.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decentralized governance requires a greater coordination effort between cantonal ministries and national bodies to ensure effective collaboration across sector and institutions. • Lack of formal communication mechanisms limits cross-sector collaboration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formalizing inter-sectoral cooperation between relevant sectors and institutions at different levels through a OH framework. • Leverage the state-level ID committee for integrating sectors and stakeholders, also replicable at the entity level.
Prevention and preparedness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust surveillance system in place, with a focus on priority zoonotic diseases. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of integrated preparedness plans for multi-sectoral health threats. • Limited emergency preparedness coordination across entities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The existing robust surveillance system, can be enhanced with the development of multisectoral prevention and preparedness plans.
Data collection and analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The FBiH has a well-developed laboratory network, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fragmented data reporting, especially in cantonal institutes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full digitalization of disease surveillance. • The comprehensive

	<p>enabling timely detection of health threats like Influenza.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The well-developed data collection system established during the COVID-19 pandemic provided valuable insights that can support ongoing surveillance efforts. 	<p>relying on paper-based methods.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delays in integrating and sharing data. 	<p>COVID-19 database, which has proven valuable for surveillance, can be leveraged to set up a similar data-driven framework for monitoring other diseases, enhancing overall public health preparedness.</p>
Capacity Building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International collaboration (e.g., WHO, Pasteur Institute) support capacity-building efforts. • Training initiatives for AMR and influenza virus isolation to strengthen expertise. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff shortages in critical sectors like epidemiology and veterinary medicine slow disease surveillance and response. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand education and training programs in entomology, epidemiology, and veterinary medicine. • Invest in specialized training for zoonotic diseases and vector-borne pathogens with the support of international collaborations • Improve recruitment and retention in critical sectors to address workforce gaps. • Establish a formal OH committee for structured cross-sector training.
Consolidation and evaluation of the system in place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The establishment of a national-level committee for infectious diseases enhances coordination among public health authorities, veterinary and environmental sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inconsistent reporting mechanisms and data-sharing practices across entities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leverage the national-level committee for infectious diseases by standardizing reporting mechanisms and data-sharing practices across entities to facilitate monitoring and evaluation of the system
Harmonisation of plans and cross-border collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active participation in regional health initiatives like AMR monitoring within the framework of European Union. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The lack of unified OH framework complicates cross border collaboration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen regional collaboration, improving shared data and joint initiatives for zoonotic diseases.

The opportunities outlined in the table 4 are proposed by considering the FBiH system characteristics identified during the study and factors facilitating national OH operationalisation emerged in the previous studies conducted in the context of MLS [8,9, 23]. The decentralized governance structure in the FBiH presents significant challenges in coordinating health authorities at the cantonal and national levels asking for efforts in OH operationalisation. Evidence from the previous MLS studies highlights the benefits of establishing centralized OH committees to ensure coordination of integrated activities. MLS cases suggest that centralized coordination frameworks might facilitate integration of OH approaches and multisectoral collaborations also in decentralized system contexts.

Other possible challenges due to the persistency of paper-based surveillance data exchange should be addressed by leveraging the digitalised systems already developed in the country. FBiH's existing COVID-19 surveillance infrastructure provides a robust foundation for expanding digitalized, interoperable systems to monitor all infectious diseases. In developing the digitalised system, the integration of environmental data should be considered specially to enhance the early warning system. Workforce shortages in epidemiology, veterinary medicine, and entomology further hinder effective disease OH preparedness in FBiH. Targeted capacity-building programs represent a clear opportunity, as demonstrated in other MLS countries where training focus in particular on zoonotic diseases like anthrax, while community-level workforce initiatives improved early detection in rural areas [8,9 23]. In addition, further opportunities with the international organisations of the Quadripartite could be considered to support capacity-building initiatives, enhance surveillance systems, and strengthen cross-sector collaboration for improved OH preparedness in FBiH.

4.6 REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA

RS is one of the two entities of Bosnia and Herzegovina, covering approximately 49% of the country's territory. Situated in the north and east, RS was formally established by the Dayton Accords in 1995. It operates under a centralized administrative structure, divided into municipalities, allowing for a more unified governance system. The city of Banja Luka serves as the administrative center of Republic of Srpska and is recognized as one of the country's major regional cities [11].

Health System in the RS

The healthcare system in RS is centralized, with the MoHSW of RS holding primary authority. This Ministry is responsible for coordinating healthcare activities, creating policies, and planning the operations of health institutions. RS operates a single health insurance fund, the Health Insurance Fund of RS (HIFRS), which pools mandatory health insurance contributions to finance the healthcare system.

These contributions are collected from various sources, including salaries, pension beneficiaries, farmers, the unemployed, and other groups [16].

Provision of healthcare services in RS is based on principles of solidarity, mutuality, and equality, ensuring that all insured persons have equal access to services regardless of their contribution amount or registration basis [24]. These services are provided through a network of public healthcare institutions, which include primary care facilities (health centers), secondary care (general and specialized hospitals), and tertiary care institutions. Access to healthcare services is available both paid and under agreements with the HIFRS of RS [16].

Public Health in RS

The public health system in RS is managed by the Institute of Public Health of RS (IPH RS), which is responsible for disease surveillance, public health research, and the implementation of public health interventions. The IPH RS plays a key role in monitoring infectious diseases, tracking health trends, and coordinating emergency responses. It works closely with the MHRS to implement health programs that address issues such as vaccination, communicable diseases, and health education.

Veterinary Sector in RS

The veterinary sector in RS operates under the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Management of RS. This Ministry is responsible for animal health care, veterinary and sanitary control in the production and trade of animals and animal products and disease control, including the management of zoonotic diseases, animal disease surveillance, vaccination programs, and ensuring food safety [25]. These responsibilities are outlined in the Veterinary Law of RS, which is enforced by the veterinary services within the Ministry.

Veterinary services in RS are centralized, with efforts to align regulations with European Union (EU) standards, particularly concerning animal health, food safety, and veterinary practices. The Veterinary Law of RS regulates veterinary activities, animal health protection, and measures for the detection, prevention, control, and eradication of infectious animal diseases. It also addresses zoonotic disease prevention, veterinary public health, animal welfare, and animal product safety.

Veterinary inspection is carried out by veterinary inspectors and food inspectors of the Republic Administration for Inspection Affairs, as well as by local self-government units within their competencies. The Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Management oversees the implementation of these regulations, ensuring supervision over the entire veterinary system, including veterinary health control of animal breeding, trade, and food safety measures for animal products and by-products. Additionally, the Ministry manages professional training in veterinary medicine, registration procedures, and the control of veterinary medical products.

The **organizational infrastructure** of the veterinary sector includes:

1. Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Management (Veterinary Department)
2. Veterinary Chamber
3. Association of Doctor of Veterinary Medicine of the RS
4. Veterinary Stations
5. Veterinary Clinics
6. Republic Inspection (Republic Administration for Inspection Affairs)
7. Veterinary Inspection in local self-government units
8. Public Institution Veterinary Institute of the RS "Dr. Vaso Butozan" Banja Luka
9. Veterinary Laboratory "Slaven" (private)
10. Veterinary Institute "Teolab" (private)

The veterinary sector in RS is also focused on aligning its practices with WHOA (World Organisation for Animal Health) standards and the EU's veterinary and food safety requirements, ensuring compliance with international animal health regulations.

Site visit and Consultations

Table 5. Overview of the consulted Institutions and their Roles in RS

Institution	Role and Responsibilities	Dates of Meetings
Ministry of Health and Social Welfare of the Republic of Srpska	Responsible for overseeing healthcare services, social welfare policies, and public health initiatives within RS. It manages health system planning, regulation, and implementation, focusing on improving healthcare access, quality, and social services for the population.	17 October 2024
Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management	Oversees agriculture, water management, forestry, and veterinary services in the RS. Its structure includes sectors for agriculture, rural development, veterinary affairs, forestry, hunting, project management, and administrative functions.	17 October 2024
Public Health Institute of Republic of Srpska	Responsible for monitoring public health, conducting epidemiological surveillance, and implementing health promotion programs within the region. It plays a key role in disease prevention, public health policy development, and improving overall health standards in RS.	18 October 2024

Public Institution Veterinary Institute of the Republic of Srpska "Dr. Vaso Butozan" Banja Luka	<p>A national scientific institution specializing in veterinary medicine. It operates through two main centers: the Center for Laboratory Testing and Quality, and the Center for Animal Health and Food Safety. The Institute also maintains a laboratory in Bijeljina to process regional samples.</p>	<p>18 October 2024</p>
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Ministry of Health and Social Welfare of Republic of Srpska

The team’s first meeting in Banja Luka was with representatives from the MoHSW of RS and the PHI of the RS. Discussions focused on regional health policies and how they align with national OH initiatives. The meeting provided valuable insights into regional approaches to disease prevention, health security, and cross-sector collaboration.

The team learned about integration efforts for the surveillance of diseases like WNV and Brucella, which are key priorities in the region. Despite strong collaboration based on long-standing personal and professional relationships, challenges remain, particularly due to the lack of formalized inter-sectoral mechanisms. The discussions also highlighted the role of various commissions, including those for zoonoses and public health, in managing health responses which could support a more coordinated approach to OH.

The importance of strengthening the integration of veterinary, human health, and environmental sectors for more effective disease surveillance and response was emphasized during the meeting.

Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of Republic of Srpska

Later in the day, the ISS team met with representatives from the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of RS, Veterinary department and the PHI of the RS. The discussion centred around the Ministry's role in managing health risks and controlling zoonotic diseases, such as Brucella, at the interface between animal health, human health, and the environment.

The Veterinary Department, a part of the Ministry, plays a critical role in the surveillance and management of animal diseases, including Brucella vaccination campaigns for small ruminants. The Department works closely with public health institutions for data sharing. However, the integration of surveillance systems remains a challenge, particularly with the lack of a fully structured system for assessing risks like WNV. The Ministry, along with veterinary offices, facilitates communication across regions, although data transfer processes are still under development.

The importance of ongoing coordination between veterinary and public health sectors, particularly in response to outbreaks, was emphasized, with a focus on improving the exchange of information. Additionally, there is a need for a more integrated IT system to support surveillance activities.

Public Health Institute of Republic of Srpska

The final meetings of the site visit took place on 18 October at the PHI of RS with the experts in surveillance from the PHI of the RS. During the meeting, the team discussed the Institute's essential role in monitoring public health and overseeing the surveillance of infectious diseases, particularly zoonotic diseases like Brucellosis.

The discussion highlighted the challenges of managing Brucellosis outbreaks, particularly in light of the 2008 crisis. The conversation also emphasized the importance of integrating animal health and environmental data into public health decision-making, especially for zoonotic diseases like Brucellosis. While the Institute has made strides in improving collaboration across sectors, significant barriers remain in data sharing and coordination. For example, the absence of a unified information system complicates the timely exchange of data between veterinary and human health sectors, hindering effective responses to outbreaks.

Despite these challenges, the Institute is committed to fostering intersectoral cooperation, recognizing it as crucial for enhancing the effectiveness of OH strategies. The Institute is actively working to improve the integration of veterinary and human health data and strengthen regional health security, ensuring a more coordinated response to infectious diseases.

Analysis of the findings

OH System Description

The RS operates with a centralized governance structure for public health and veterinary services, coordinated by the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare and the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of RS. These sectors work closely together to address zoonotic diseases and other public health threats, with decision making facilitated by the Commission for Zoonoses, which plays a crucial role in coordinating responses to emergency health threats. Veterinary data is collected and processed through the Veterinary Information System (VIS), which facilitates communication with the human health sector. Monthly reports and bulletins are exchanged between the veterinary and public health sectors to ensure timely coordination, with the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of RS and the Veterinary Institute playing key roles in managing disease outbreaks. RS has made significant progress in digitalizing its veterinary data through the VIS, which supports the management of animal health, vaccinations, and disease outbreaks. However, while the VIS is fully digitalized, the public health sector's data reporting system remains less streamlined, with some data still managed manually or through disconnected systems. Collaborations are in place with Montenegro, Slovenia and Croatia.

Table 6. System analysis based on the OHCF Pillars

Pillar	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities
Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VIS digitalization strengthens governance by centralizing animal health data and improving sectoral coordination. • Cross-border collaborations with Croatia, Slovenia and Montenegro enhance regional governance through coordinated responses and data sharing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited integration of human and veterinary health data reduces disease management efficiency, despite the VIS digitalization. • Lack of formal coordination procedures and mechanisms between sectors delays decision-making. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formalizing cross-border collaboration can be achieved through agreements for data exchange and joint initiatives, ensuring coordinated responses during emergencies.
Prevention and Preparedness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established vaccination programs and strong surveillance systems for zoonotic diseases, such as brucella and anthrax. • Coordination with international organizations supports effective disease control and prevention. • Collaborative efforts during the COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated successful cross-sector cooperation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate surveillance for vector-borne diseases like WNV, might lead to delays in local diagnostics and response. • Non-operational BLS3 laboratories limit diagnostic capabilities for high-risk diseases. • Lack of integrated preparedness plans for multi-sectoral health threats. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanding surveillance to include emerging zoonotic diseases like WNV and integrating environmental data can be achieved by enhancing diagnostic systems. • Establishing a unified OH preparedness plan across human, animal, and environmental health sectors can be achieved by developing a comprehensive strategy that integrates all sectors, with clear roles, regular updates, and joint training programs.
Data Collection and Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digitalized systems like VIS improve data collection and integration for effective disease management. • Regular data exchange between veterinary and public health sectors ensures timely responses and better coordination. Monthly reports and bulletins exchanged between the veterinary and public health sectors facilitate data analysis, risk and trends assessments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliance on paper-based reporting methods in some regions causes delays in data sharing and response. • the environmental data system in RS should be able to provide data to the other sectors to enhance comprehensive monitoring and coordination across sectors in terms of early warning for those OH threats impacted by environmental aspects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building on lessons learned from the VIS platform, an interoperable digital platform could be developed for integrating human, veterinary, and environmental health data, enhancing surveillance and early warning capabilities. • integration environmental data in surveillance systems
Capacity Building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OH, education programs and courses have been introduced at universities, providing specialized training in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persistent staff shortages, particularly in veterinary and epidemiological sectors, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted recruitment and professional development to address staffing shortages

	zoonotic disease management, which enhances the capacity to address emerging health threats.	limit response effectiveness.	• Identification of common sectors' priorities to valorise the skills and competencies of the available staff
Consolidation and Evaluation of the System in place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active inter-ministerial collaboration during health crises. • Commission for zoonoses facilitates decision-making by serving as a coordinating body that brings together public health, veterinary and environmental sectors to address zoonotic disease risk in structured manner 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • no periodic review of health strategies and plans with a OH lens. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review and update health strategies and plans with a OH approach regularly • Involve all the relevant stakeholders in the review process • Engage the Zoonoses Commission's work to streamline the review process
Harmonisation of plans and cross border collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active participation in regional disease control programs and health networks. • Collaboration between veterinary and human health sectors, especially for zoonotic diseases like Brucella. • Cross-border collaboration with neighbouring countries like Croatia, Slovenia, and Montenegro. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of standardized cross-border strategies and weak coordination between RS and FBiH hinder effective health management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leveraging the Brucella outbreak lessons learnt to improve cross-border health responses • Leveraging the existing Commission for Zoonoses and expanding its role to include municipal and district-level representation could strengthen coordination and information sharing among public health, veterinary, and environmental sectors. • Expanding regional collaborations also with the organisation of simulation exercises will enhance preparedness and response.

The opportunities outlined in the table 6 are proposed by considering the OH system characteristics identified during the study and factors facilitating OH operationalisation emerged in the previous studies conducted in the context of MLS [8,9, 23].

While VIS digitalization has improved animal health data management, the absence of integrated human, veterinary, and environmental health data limits its effectiveness.

The development of an interoperable platform in RS, where referents of the institutions involved in the surveillance of threats benefiting from an OH approach can upload surveillance specific data and have access to other data uploaded by other institutions, could be a solution that facilitates integrated risk assessment, early warning and surveillance. These selected data should come from sectorial digitalised systems which are connected with the interoperable OH platform.

The opportunity to expand surveillance for VBDs, such as WNV, is particularly crucial given the gaps in local diagnostics and preparedness and integrating environmental and climatic data into the health systems can enable climate-driven mapping to improve detection and response.

Addressing staff shortages in the veterinary and epidemiological sectors presents another opportunity to build long-term capacity. Workforce gaps might be addressed by enhancing collaboration with international organisations including those of the Quadripartite and providing professional development opportunities through partnerships with international organizations.

Also, identify priorities common to the relevant sectors involved in the surveillance of zoonoses, can optimise the work of the available staff and reduce the possible impact due to the workforce shortage. Leveraging the existing Commission for Zoonoses and expanding its role to include representation from all administrative levels of RS could ensure structured communication, streamline decision-making, and enable harmonized responses to emerging health threats. Conducting joint simulation exercises with neighbouring countries (will further enhance preparedness and strengthen regional collaboration.

RS's lack of formal evaluation mechanisms for its OH strategies limits opportunities for system refinement and the conduction of periodic evaluations of the surveillance and preparedness systems, involving relevant stakeholders can facilitate OH operationalisation.

4.7 BRČKO DISTRICT OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

Brčko District is a unique administrative unit in BiH, established under the Brčko Final Award of 1999, following a decision by the Arbitral Tribunal of the United Nations (UN). It is a self-governing district that is not part of either of the two entities (FBiH or RS), making it a special case in BiH's political structure. The district is located in the northeaster part of the country, on the banks of the Sava River, and covers a relatively small area of approximately 493 square kilometres, with a population of around 80,000. The city of Brčko is both the capital and the largest city of the district [25].

The district is jointly owned by both entities (the FBiH and RS) but is independently self-governed [26]. The local government is responsible for most areas of public administration, including health, education, and infrastructure. Brčko District operates under its own statute and laws, while still being subject to the Constitution of BiH. It has a different level of autonomy compared to the FBiH and RS, as it is not an entity itself but a special administrative unit.

Health System in Brčko District

Brčko District operates an independent healthcare system, separate from the entities of the FBiH and RS. The healthcare system is managed by the Department of Health and Other Services, which is part of the government of Brčko District. This department is responsible for implementing health policies, regulating healthcare services, and overseeing public health programs. The Health Insurance Fund (HiF) of Brčko District provides mandatory health insurance, covering health services at primary, secondary, and tertiary levels within the district [16]. The healthcare system is primarily funded through mandatory health insurance contributions, a model consistent with other regions in BiH. All residents, including employed individuals, students, pensioners, and the unemployed, are included in the system [27].

Veterinary Sector in Brčko District

The veterinary sector in Brčko District operates within the complex institutional framework of BiH. The VOBiH, under the Ministry of Foreign Trade and Economic Relations BiH, serves as the umbrella institution coordinating veterinary activities across the country. Brčko District, along with the FBiH and RS, maintains its own veterinary service responsible for monitoring and controlling infectious diseases, including zoonoses. The Veterinary Inspectorate of Brčko District oversees this territory. Like the entities, veterinary services in Brčko District operate in accordance with BiH's Veterinary Law of 2002, which established a unified sector system for the country. This law allows Brčko District to issue its own veterinary legislation while remaining aligned with national standards [18].

In addition, the veterinary sector in Brčko District, alongside the entities, participates in national disease control and eradication programs. For example, Brčko District was involved in the implementation of the Operational Programme for the Prevention of Brucellosis, which included the vaccination of small ruminants [18].

Environmental Health in Brčko District

Environmental health is a key priority in Brčko District, although the governance structure differs from other regions. Unlike other areas, Brčko District does not have a dedicated Ministry of Environment and Tourism. Instead, environmental issues are managed by the Department for Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management and the Department of Public Health, both of which fall under the Brčko District government.

Brčko District is involved in the EU's Green Agenda for the Western Balkans, a regional initiative aimed at promoting sustainable development and environmental protection. The Green Agenda addresses challenges such as decarbonization, the circular economy, biodiversity conservation, pollution reduction, and the development of sustainable food systems and rural areas [28]. Launched by the European Commission in October 2020, the Green Agenda encourages regional governments to utilize EU funds for environmental protection and sustainable development. However, its

implementation has faced challenges, including a lack of clear structure, timelines, and targeted reporting mechanisms [29].

Efforts to improve environmental health in Brčko District align with broader national initiatives, which include improving air and water quality, reducing the environmental impact of industrial activities, and enhancing waste management, particularly in urban areas. While specific details about Brčko District's environmental initiatives are not fully available, it is clear that the district participates in national programs aimed at improving environmental sustainability and health.

Table 7. OH System analysis of Brčko District based on the OHCF Pillars

Pillar	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities
Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective coordination with RS for public health management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of formal coordination between Brčko, RS, and FBiH delays responses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen formal coordination with RS and FBiH.
Prevention and preparedness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brčko District's unified administrative structure facilitates streamlined decision making. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of a developed OH roadmap for preparedness. • Insufficient entomology and environmental surveillance capacity including limited laboratory resources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a comprehensive OH roadmap in synergies with RS and FBiH.
Data collection and analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly disease reports submitted to RS, supporting public health monitoring, and to the PHI of Tuzla canton (Federation of BiH), and to the MoCA of BiH (for the epidemiology sector) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the absence of a centralized electronic database slow down information exchange. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand data collection capacities by adopting electronic data-sharing practices in synergies with RS and FBiH.
Capacity Building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well trained and specialised workforce available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited trained professionals in key sectors like epidemiology. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted training programs for zoonotic disease management. • Enhance surveillance expertise in entomology and the environmental sciences
Consolidation and evaluation of the system in place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functional disease reporting and coordination with RS and FBiH. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of formal evaluation systems to assess efficiency and level of integration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish formal evaluation systems to improve disease control with a OH lens

The opportunities outlined in the table 7 are proposed by considering the Brčko District's system characteristics identified during the study and factors facilitating national OH operationalisation emerged in the previous studies conducted in the context of MLS [8,9,23].

Brčko District faces unique governance challenges due to the absence of a dedicated ministry for environmental health, which affects early warning capacities for OH threats. While there is effective coordination with RS, formalized agreements with RS and the FBiH would streamline decision-making and ensure a unified response. Addressing staffing shortages in epidemiology through targeted recruitment programs and optimisation of the available workforce would further strengthen preparedness.

The lack of a OH roadmap limits Brčko District's ability to manage multi-sectoral health threats effectively. Developing an integrated strategy that aligns human, veterinary, and environmental sectors will improve preparedness for zoonotic and vector-borne diseases.

Limited data collection mechanisms including the absence of a centralized electronic database further constrain Brčko District's surveillance capacity. Although monthly disease reports are submitted to RS, FBiH and MoCA adopting a digital reporting system with an interoperable platform that integrates environmental data would enhance multi-sectoral coordination, risk assessment and surveillance capacities.

Capacity building offers another opportunity to address workforce shortages in critical sectors like entomology and environmental surveillance. Brčko can build a skilled workforce capable of effectively monitoring and responding to zoonotic and vector-borne health threats in synergy with RS and FBiH.

4.8 ONLINE CONSULTATIONS

Consultations were run also online with experts not available during the planned site visit.

In particular, an online meeting was held on the 18 September 2024 with representatives from UNEP. The discussions focused on enhancing coordination between the public health and environmental sectors, as well as formulating strategic approaches to address critical health and environmental challenges within the country.

Also, an online meeting was conducted in September with Dr. Adi Edi Kaloper, Department of Health and Other Services of Brčko District of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Sub-Department for Public Health), to discuss information related to the OH system in Brčko District.

5 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Although the mapping of the relevant stakeholders was started since the beginning of the study, some stakeholders might have been missing during the consultation as the case of the representatives of the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Water Management, and Forestry (FMPVŠ).

The revision of the Report by all the national institutions involved has helped to fill the information gaps.

Representatives of all the institutions of the FBiH, the RS and Brčko District of BiH relevant to the study's aim were involved, they jointly participated to the online meetings, but unfortunately it was not possible to have a meeting involving together the Entities and the District during the site visit.

6 CONCLUSION AND WAY FORWARD

The OHMeSA in BiH emphasizes the need for integrating a OH approach to effectively address emerging health threats, particularly zoonoses and vector-borne diseases. While BiH faces challenges due to its different governance structure, considering its constitution in two Entities and one District, it also provides an opportunity for more localized, context-driven solutions. The study highlights key strengths, such as existing infrastructure and regional collaborations, which provide a solid foundation for strengthening the OH approach. However, there is a need for enhanced coordination across human, veterinary, and environmental health sectors. Strengthening cross-border collaborations and capacity-building initiatives will be crucial in addressing these challenges and enhancing the overall health system preparedness.

To strengthen and integrate the OH approach, a few aspects might deserve common attention by the Entities and the District of BiH, even in light of their peculiar characteristics.

Leveraging on the Committees already available for the control of infectious diseases, enlargement to additional disciplines and sectors could be considered, also extending representativeness to relevant organs (public and private) not included at the moment of this assessment.

Interoperable digital systems need to be implemented in each of the two Entities and Brčko District in BiH, to share data and information presently rarely shared in real time between sectors and therefore preventing early warning actions. Environmental health data should be also integrated.

Some efforts to enhance the availability of One Health sessions in training curricula have been implemented and further opportunities can be explored to facilitate access of workforce to training in the context of international projects and networks.

7 ANNEXES

- Annex I_ Check list WNV
- Annex II_ Check list Brucellosis
- Annex III_ Check list OHCF
- Annex IV_ Country Portfolio

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iii. Is a **National coordinating unit** in place? YES NO

a. If YES

i. Role: _____

ii. Members: _____

iii. frequency of ordinary meetings: _____

iv. reasons for extraordinary meetings: _____

v. ways of communication between members: _____

vi.

iv. Is there a **coordinated plan for distribution of human resources** dedicated to surveillance among the different sectors? YES NO

v. Is a **plan** for WNV Integrated surveillance available? YES NO

If YES, is it prepared on annual basis? YES NO

If YES, is the 2024 plan available? (to be provided if available) YES NO

vi. Are **types and targets** of surveillance identified in the plan? YES NO

vii. Are Endemic and not-endemic areas identified? YES NO

2. Level of integration: Data collection and analysis

Endemic area

- Surveillance of migratory birds belonging to the target species YES NO
 - o Seasonal
 - o Permanent

If YES:

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- Surveillance in rural poultry farms and outdoor YES NO
 - o Seasonal
 - o Permanent

If YES:

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- Surveillance through the use of sentinel groups of animals YES NO
 - o Seasonal
 - o Permanent

If YES:

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- | | | |
|-------------------------------------|-----|----|
| - <u>Entomological Surveillance</u> | YES | NO |
| ○ Seasonal | | |
| ○ Permanent | | |

If YES:

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- | | | |
|--------------------------------------|-----|----|
| - <u>Surveillance of human cases</u> | YES | NO |
| ○ Seasonal | | |
| ○ Permanent | | |

If YES:

Who is in charge for the epi surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

Who is in charge for the lab surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

Surveillance in all the areas of the Country?

YES NO

If YES:

- Clinical surveillance in equidae

YES NO

- Seasonal
- Permanent

If YES:

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- Serological sampling surveillance in equidae

YES NO

- Seasonal
- Permanent

If YES:

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- Surveillance of wild birds' carcasses

YES NO

- Seasonal
- Permanent

If YES:

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- | | | |
|--|-----|----|
| - <u>Serological Surveillance on sample of animals</u> | YES | NO |
| ○ Seasonal | | |
| ○ Permanent | | |

If YES:

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

• **Early Warning – Risk Assessment-Response-Communication**

Is there any early warning system, which activates human health measures based on animal and /or entomological surveillance? YES NO

If YES, can you describe your role (organizer, participant, etc.) in the process as per the table below? Is the procedure formally developed and available? YES NO

Steps of the Process	EW	Risk assessment	Response/Public Health Actions	Risk Communication
How does the process start? or What event triggers the process to start?				
You provide info to (Institution/s; Dept/s)				
Type of info				
how soon/periodicity				
Info are provided to you by (Institution/s; Dept/s)				
Type of info				
how soon/periodicity				
Multisectorial meetings (periodicity)				
report exchange (periodicity)				

- Please describe the most recent early warning case and provide available documents

• **USE of data for PUBLIC HEALTH ACTIONS**

Is a national database available for surveillance data? YES NO

If YES, is this database including all the surveillance data (animal, entomological, human) YES NO

If NO, which kind of database are available?

Are they accessible to other sectors involved in the surveillance? YES NO

If YES,

- specify the sector/s: _____
- type of access: consultation data management

3. Level of integration: Dissemination

Is a communication dept. /officer available? YES NO

If YES, is this connected/coordinated with the other relevant sectors? YES NO

Is a National bulletin/newsletter jointly prepared by all the relevant sectors available?

YES NO

If YES:

Frequency: _____

Target/s: _____

Is a dedicated website jointly managed by all the relevant sectors available? YES NO

Is the Evaluation of the integrated WNV plan performed? YES NO

If YES, is this available? YES NO

4. Enabling factors to strengthen an integrated surveillance system for WNV

- I. Are there **policies supporting local actions for WNV** bringing together local actors (public and private) and national actors? YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these policies?

If NO which enabling factors could support the development of local policies?

What factors could hamper them?

- II. Are there **initiatives advocating for the importance of the OH approach for WNV** prevention and preparedness? YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these initiatives?

If NO which enabling factors could support awareness initiatives?

What factors could hamper them?

- III. Are there **mechanism supporting the strict collaboration** of human, animal and environmental health and medical entomology for WNV prevention and preparedness? YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these mechanisms?

If NO which enabling factors could support collaboration mechanisms?

What factors could hamper them?

IV. Are there **trainings about OH prevention and preparedness to WNV?** YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these trainings?

If NO which enabling factors could support the development of these trainings?

What factors could hamper them?

V. Are there **integrated operational strategies** such as plans, procedures for data sharing, procedures for risk communication etc. both at national and local level supporting prevention and preparedness to WNV? YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these strategies?

If NO which enabling factors could support the development of these strategies?

What factors could hamper them?

VI. Are there **integrated research studies** targeting prevention and preparedness to WNV?

YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these studies?

If NO which enabling factors could support the development of these studies?

What factors could hamper them?

VII. Are there **projects/programs/networks** targeting WNV in your country with a OH approach that could enhance the harmonization of prevention and preparedness among countries?

YES NO

If YES which ones?

Which enabling factors supported these projects/programs/networks?

If NO which enabling factors could support the development of these projects/programs/networks?

What factors could hamper them?

vi.

iii. Is a **National coordinating unit** in place ? YES NO

a. If YES

i. Role: _____

ii. Members: _____

iii. frequency of ordinary meetings: _____

iv. reasons for extraordinary meetings: _____

v. ways of communication between members: _____

vi.

iv. Is there a **coordinated plan for distribution of human resources** dedicated to surveillance among the different sectors? YES NO

v. Is a **plan** for Brucellosis Integrated surveillance available? YES NO

If YES, is it prepared on annual basis? YES NO

If YES, is the 2024 plan available? (to be provided if available) YES NO

vi. Are **types and targets** of surveillance identified in the plan? YES NO

vii. Are Endemic and not-endemic areas identified ? YES NO

2. Level of integration: Data collection and analysis

Who is in charge for the surveillance in animal (institution, Dept. etc):

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- Surveillance through the use of sentinel groups of animals YES NO

If YES:

Who is in charge for the surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

- Surveillance of human cases YES NO

If YES:

Who is in charge for the epi surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

Who is in charge for the lab surveillance (institution, Dept. etc): _____

who does the analysis (institution, Dept. etc): _____

to whom the confirmed cases are reported (institution/s, Dept/s. etc) : _____

timing : _____

way/s: _____

Surveillance in all the areas of the Country?

YES NO

If YES:

- **Early Warning – Risk Assessment-Response-Communication**

Is there any early warning system, which activates human health measures based on animal surveillance?

YES NO

If YES, can you describe your role (organizer, participant, etc.) in the process as per the table below? Is the procedure formally developed and available? YES NO

Steps of the Process	EW	Risk assessment	Response/Public Health Actions	Risk Communication
How does the process start? or What event triggers the process to start?				
You provide info to (Institution/s; Dept/s)				
Type of info				
how soon/periodicity				
Info are provided to you by (Institution/s; Dept/s)				
Type of info				
how soon/periodicity				
Multisectorial meetings (periodicity)				

report exchange (periodicity)				
----------------------------------	--	--	--	--

- Please describe the most recent early warning case and provide available documents

• **USE of data for PUBLIC HEALTH ACTIONS**

Is a national database available for surveillance data? YES NO

If YES, is this database including all the surveillance data (animal, human, etc.) YES NO

If NO, which kind of database are available?

Are they accessible to other sectors involved in the surveillance? YES NO

If YES,

- specify the sector/s: _____

- type of access: consultation data management

3. Level of integration: Dissemination

Is a communication dept. /officer available? YES NO

If YES, is this connected/coordinated with the other relevant sectors? YES NO

Is a National bulletin/newsletter jointly prepared by all the relevant sectors available?

YES NO

If YES:

Frequency: _____

Target/s: _____

Is a dedicated website jointly managed by all the relevant sectors available? YES NO

Is the Evaluation of the integrated Brucellosis plan performed? YES NO

If YES, is this available? YES NO

Priority 1: Governance¹

1.1. Policy and legislation

- ✓ Existing policy and legislative OH instruments, such as policies, strategies, frameworks, standards, roadmaps, laws, norms etc.

Description:

Resources

- ✓ Existing multisectoral funds, financial mechanisms
- ✓ Performed cost-benefit analysis and/or a business case of the One Health
- ✓ Dedicated personnel to support OH strategies and practices
- ✓ Assets/equipment sharing

Have the establishment of a National One Health platform with OH stakeholders [3,4] or a OH National Center considered?

1.2. Collaboration mechanisms

- ✓ Existing initiatives like multisectoral and multistakeholder teams/mechanisms
Description (type, date, actors and roles, sectors, activities during emergency and non-emergency periods)
- ✓ Guidelines to enable transparent information sharing
- ✓ Gender-sensitive regulatory frameworks

¹ Refer to [2] for some considerations on key attributes of Governance for the successful implementation of OH initiatives

1.3. Advocacy

- ✓ Existing multisectoral and multistakeholder methodologies and tools to raise awareness, advocate for and promote the OH approach at all levels

1.4. Global and international governance

- ✓ Cross-border/regional meetings/workshops/mechanisms to develop/harmonize action plans
- ✓ International collaborations to support One Health policies and legislation
- ✓ Adoption/implement international guidance (Quadripartite)

Priority 2: PREVENTION AND PREPAREDNESS

2.1. Specific OH prevention/preparedness plans:

Description

Institutions/stakeholders involved in the plans:

Status: Development; implementation; monitoring; updating

2.2. Joint One Health risk assessments

Description

2.3. Risk factors and drivers mapping, as well as solutions for risk mitigation

Description

2.4. Processes and guidelines for risk communication and community engagement

Description

2.5. Communication strategies developed for decision-makers

Description

Priority 3: DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Existing integrated surveillance systems

3.2. Integrated and interoperable database connected with early warning and surveillance systems established

Description (governance of the database, stakeholders etc.)

Dashboards and maps depicting the epidemiological disease situation

Mapping available sources of information and data

3.3. Are there procedures to support Information sharing among sectors and stakeholders for outbreak prevention, preparedness, response

3.4. Are Operational Tools, like the Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Tool (SIS-OT), adopted to establish or strengthen coordinated One Health surveillance and information sharing systems

3.6. Are there procedures to support Integrated data reporting

3.7. Are there procedures to support Multisectoral predictive risk analysis

Priority 4: CAPACITY BUILDING, TRAINING

- 4.1. Are there procedures to support the development of training curricula based on One Health prevention and preparedness:
- 4.2. Existing OH training for OH workforce
- 4.3. Piloting and exercising (eg. simulation exercises)
- 4.4. OH networking initiatives
- 4.5. Operational tools and equipment for integrated practices provided (eg. Surveillance, biohazard containment etc.)

Priority 5: CONSOLIDATION AND EVALUATION OF THE SYSTEM IN PLACE [5,6,7,8]

- 5.1. OH M&E framework established with monitoring and impact multisectoral indicators
- 5.2. implementation of already existing evaluation tools and roadmaps at all levels
- 5.3. OH evaluation plan in place or performed
- 5.4. Were exercises like JEE, OIE-PVS evaluations, After Action Reviews performed? Were gaps addressed?

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Annex IV

OHMESA STUDY IN BOSNIA & HERZEGOVINA

COUNTRY PORTFOLIO

(version finalised on 8 October 2024)

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

- BHAS: Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina
- BiH: Bosnia and Herzegovina
- CCHFV: Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever Virus
- CE: Cystic Echinococcosis
- EBRD: European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
- EU: European Union
- FBiH: Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina
- FAIA: Federal Administration for Inspection Affairs
- GDP: Gross Domestic Product
- HFRS: Health Insurance Fund of Republic of Srpska
- LLOV: Lloviu virus
- MoFTER: Ministry of Foreign Trade and Economic Relations
- MLS: MediLabSecure
- MoCA: Ministry of Civil Affairs of Bosnia and Herzegovina
- OH: One Health
- RS: Republic of Srpska
- SVO: State Veterinary Office
- VO BiH: Veterinary Office of Bosnia and Herzegovina
- WHO: World Health Organization
- WOA: World Organisation for Animal Health

1. Geographic, Demographic, Governance, and Socio-Economic Profile of Bosnia and Herzegovina

1.1 Geography

Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) is located in the western Balkan Peninsula of Europe, bordering Croatia to the north, northwest and south, and Serbia and Montenegro to the east. The largest part of the territory consists of mountains and high karst, covered by forests and pastures. The highest peak is Maglić (2,386 m). Lowlands are in the north and southwest. BiH has access to the Adriatic Sea near the town of Neum, although very narrow strip (21.2 km). The climate in the northern part is temperate continental, in the central part mountainous, while in the southern part it is Mediterranean. The capital of the country is Sarajevo; important regional cities include Banja Luka, Mostar and Tuzla.

Although country name suggests that the country is constituted from Bosnia and Herzegovina, these are geographical and historical regions, where Bosnia largely is in the northern and central part of the country and Herzegovina in a land strip located in the south and southwest.

Figure.1– Bosnia and Herzegovina geography (www.alamy.com)

1.2 Population

According to the latest census of 2013, BiH had a population of 3,531,159, which was slightly over 3.5 million, and this number is declining. The population figures for the entities in 2013 were: Federation of BiH (FBiH) with 2,219,220, Republic of Srpska (RS) with 1,228,423, and Brčko District with 83,516 [1].

BiH is a multi-ethnic country split along religious lines. The main Abrahamic religions are present in BiH and are the foundation for ethnic divisions in the country: Bosniak Muslims, Catholic Croats, Orthodox Christian Serbs, and a minority presence of Jews [2].

1.3. Administrative organization and governmental structure

BiH consists of two autonomous political entities:

1. The FBiH (about 51% of the territory) occupying the western and central areas.
2. The RS (about 49% of the territory), located in the north and east

Brčko District is an administrative unit with its own government, established by the Final Award of the Arbitration Tribunal on March 5, 1999. It is defined as a self-governing territory under the sovereignty of BiH, with its area jointly owned by (a condominium of) the two entities, but governed by its own institutions, laws, and regulations [3].

Figure.2 – BiH Entities and District- Source:alrmaps.com

BiH has a complex system of government. Governance is managed at multiple levels, with the BiH Council of Ministers at the national level, the Government of the FBiH, and the self-governing Brčko District [4]. The FBiH is further divided into ten cantons, each with its own government and significant autonomy in areas such as education and healthcare. Both FBiH and RS have their own presidents, governments, and parliaments. The lowest level of government consists of municipalities, with 84 in FBiH and 63 in RS [5].

Figure.3– Overview of the Governmental Structure (Developed on the basis of [5]).

1.4 Environmental challenges in Bosnia and Herzegovina

Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) face significant environmental challenges, particularly in the areas of air quality and energy production. The country experiences severe air pollution, especially in urban areas, with Sarajevo being particularly prone to heavy smog during winter months [6].

Air quality issues

Sarajevo's air pollution problem is exacerbated by several factors:

1. Geographical location (prone to temperature inversions)
2. High pollution levels from residential heating and traffic
3. Industrial emissions [6].

Other cities like Tuzla and Zenica also suffer from poor air quality, with particulate matter concentrations regularly exceeding legal limits [7].

Energy Sector Contributions

The energy sector is a major contributor to air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions in BiH:

- Residential heating, often relying on coal and wood, is a major source of pollutants [8].
- Coal-fired power plants generate a significant portion of the country's electricity [9]
- The country has historically had high subsidies for coal in its economy [9].

BiH faces several challenges in addressing its environmental issues due to fragmented institutional and policy framework for air quality management: lack of a comprehensive strategy for phasing out coal and lack of stronger coordination between different levels of government [9,10].

Despite these challenges, there are signs of progress:

- The World Bank approved a €46.10 million loan for an Air Quality Improvement Project in 2023 [10]
- The European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) is supporting renewable energy projects, such as a 50 MWp solar power plant [11]
- BiH has set a target of 43.6% renewable energy share by 2030 [11]

BiH is increasingly vulnerable to climate change impacts, including more frequent and severe natural hazards such as droughts, heat waves, and floods, as well as risks to agriculture and human health from changing weather patterns [12]. The country's geographical position and economic reliance on agriculture and forestry sectors exacerbate its vulnerability to these climate-related challenges [13]

According to the World Bank, to address these challenges and continue its development progress, BiH needs to implement structural economic and energy reforms, improve coordination between government levels, and align with European Union environmental standards. These reforms are crucial for enhancing the country's resilience to climate shocks, driving economic growth, and progressing towards EU membership [14].

1.5 Economic and Demographic Overview

BiH is classified as a middle-income country, with a Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita of approximately \$8,670 in 2024, which is significantly lower than the European Union (EU) average of \$45,240 [15].

BiH has demonstrated notable economic progress in recent years, particularly in reducing unemployment rates. According to the Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina (BHAS), the unemployment rate decreased from 13.2% in 2023 to 12.2% in the third quarter of 2024, marking a 1 percentage point decline. This represents a 7.6% reduction, achieving the lowest unemployment rate in recent years for BiH [16].

Healthcare expenditure plays a crucial role in BiH's economy, accounting for a significant share of public spending. As of 2021, BiH allocated 9.56% of its GDP to healthcare, which is considered high and on par with the EU average of 10.56%. However, despite this high percentage of GDP allocation, the per capita spending on healthcare in BiH remains significantly lower than the EU average [17].

Regarding out-of-pocket expenses, private healthcare spending in BiH is relatively high. As of 2021, private expenditure accounted for 30.7% of total health expenditure in BiH, which is higher than the EU average of 23.5% [17]. This high level of private spending suggests that citizens in BiH face significant out-of-pocket healthcare expenses.

To address these challenges, the World Bank approved a \$75 million loan in January 2025 to support BiH's efforts to strengthen the financial sustainability of its healthcare system and enhance the quality of health services for citizens [17]. This initiative aims to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of healthcare delivery in the country.

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2. Health Systems in Bosnia and Herzegovina

BiH has a complex healthcare framework shaped by its post-war political structure. It consists of three separate systems corresponding to the country's main political entities : the FBiH, RS, and Brčko District. Each of these entities has its own health system, governance structure, and healthcare delivery mechanisms, leading to varying degrees of access, quality, and funding. Due to this complex institutional structure the country has in total 14 ministries/departments in charge of health and 13 health insurance funds (2 entity, 1 district, 10 cantonal in the FBiH).

There is no national mandate for health care financing and provision in BiH. Health care finance, management and organization in BiH is the responsibility of each entity, and Brčko District runs a health care system under its own authority [18].

Ministry of Civil Affairs of Bosnia and Herzegovina

According to Article 15 of the Law on Ministries and Other Bodies of Administration of BiH („Official Gazette of BiH”, No. 5/03, 42/03, 26/04, 42/04, 45/06 and 88/07 and 35/09), the Ministry of Civil Affairs of BiH is responsible for tasks of citizenship, citizen registration and records, personal data protection, residency registration, identity documents, travel documents and vehicle registration process, as well as mine action.

Additionally, the Ministry is responsible for carrying out tasks and discharging duties which are within the competence of BiH and relate to defining basic principles, coordinating activities and harmonizing plans of the Entity authorities and defining a strategy at the international level in the field of: health and social care, pensions, science and education, labor and employment, culture and sport, geodetic, geological and meteorological affairs.

The activities of monitoring and coordination in the field of health, representation of BiH at the international level in the field of health, as well as ensuring high level of harmonization of health issues with the standards of the international community and meeting international obligations are realized through the Sector of Health within the MoCA, at the level of BiH.

Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina Health System

The health system in the FBiH is decentralized, with healthcare responsibilities divided among ten cantons and a federal level. Each canton operates its own Ministry of Health, responsible for overseeing healthcare services within its jurisdiction. Meanwhile, the Federal Ministry of Health plays a coordinating role, managing public health activities and facilitating the implementation of health policies across the Federation [19].

Due to the decentralized nature of the health system, the Ministry of Health in FBiH has limited responsibilities. The 10 cantonal governments hold primary responsibility for planning and delivering health insurance and healthcare services. This fragmented governance structure, involving multiple decision-makers, presents significant challenges in health policy-making. As a result, inconsistencies in healthcare management and delivery are observed across cantons [19].

The FBiH operates a decentralized health financing system. Each canton manages its own healthcare financing, which leads to significant variations in healthcare coverage and resource allocation between

cantons. The primary source of public funds is through mandatory health insurance contributions, which are collected and pooled at the canton level.

In 2020, the overall health insurance coverage rate in FBiH was 87%, but there were variations between cantons. For example, Herzegovina-Neretva Canton had 84% coverage, while Sarajevo Canton had nearly universal coverage at 100%. These figures may fluctuate due to internal migration between cantons and the outmigration of citizens. In the FBiH, children under the age of 18 without insurance are entitled to full healthcare benefits. For uninsured adults, a range of essential services is provided, including emergency care, care during pregnancy, treatment for severe mental illnesses, and chronic diseases [19].

Public Health Emergencies are managed by the Federal Ministry of Health and cantonal ministries in Federation on basis of the Law on the Protection of the Population from Infectious Diseases (Official Gazette of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina", issue 29/05).

In Federation of BiH Ministry of Labor and Social Politics manages social welfare programs on basis of the Law On The Basis Of Social Protection, Protection Of Civil Victims Of War And Protection Of Families With Children FBiH "Official Gazette of FBiH", no. 36/1999, 54/2004, 39/2006, 14/2009, 7/2014 - decision of the US BiH, 45/2016, 19/2017, 40/2018, 52/2022, 16/2023 and 60/2023)

Republic of Srpska Health System

RS has a centralized healthcare system with the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare holding primary authority. RS operates a single health insurance fund, which pools mandatory health insurance contributions to finance its healthcare system [20].

The health care system includes various institutions such as the Public Health Institute and the Health Insurance Fund of Republic of Srpska (HIF RS). The health care financing in RS is primarily based on contributions for health insurance, like the FBiH. These contributions constitute the main source of the Fund's income, including contributions paid from salaries, by pension beneficiaries, farmers, for the unemployed, and other categories [20].

The health care system in RS is based on principles of solidarity and availability, with a focus on an integral approach to healthcare delivery. The system is predominantly financed from compulsory health insurance contributions, with the HIF RS playing a key role in managing these contributions. Health care services are delivered at primary, secondary, and tertiary levels [20].

Public Health Emergencies are managed by the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare in Republic of Srpska based on the Law on the Protection of the Population from Infectious Diseases (Official Gazette of Republic of Srpska, issue 90/17, 42/20, 98/20, 63/22).

Social welfare programs are managed by the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare in Republic of Srpska on basis of the Law on Social Protection (Official Gazette of Republic of Srpska, issue 37/2012, 90/2016, 94/2019, 42/2020, 36/2022).

Brčko District Health System

Brčko District operates an independent healthcare system, separate from the entities of FBiH and RS. The district has its own Department of Health and other services in the government, as well as a Health Insurance Fund.

In accordance with the Statute of Brčko District and the Health Insurance Law of Brčko District, the Department of Health carries out professional, administrative, and other duties within the powers and competencies of the Government which relate to the health sector [20].

The health care financing in Brčko District is performed through the Health Insurance Fund, primarily from contributions paid for employed, unemployed, retired persons, self-employed, farmers, and other categories. The Assembly of the Brčko District, at the proposal of the Health Insurance Fund, passes the Decision on the base and rate of contribution for health insurance [20].

The district has its own law making and law implementation institutions (Assembly of Brčko district, Government of Brčko district and Court of Brčko district). Based on the Law on Health care of Brčko district of BiH, healthcare services are provided at primary, secondary, and tertiary levels, with a special form of health protection organized through the public health. The primary, secondary and tertiary levels are provided by the Public Health Institution 'Zdravstveni centar Brčko' which includes the Brčkos hospital and other services. The public Health is provided by the Department for Health and other services of the Government of Brčko district of BiH.

The Department of Health and Other Services carries out professional, administrative and other tasks within the competence of the Government that relate to:

- Prevention and protection of the health of the population and the functioning of the health care institutions of the Brčko District of BiH,
- Preserving and improving the health of citizens,
- analysis and monitoring of the health status and health needs of the citizens of the Brčko District of BiH,
- Creation and implementation of health policy and strategy as a whole,
- development and improvement of the health care and health insurance system,
- Monitoring and enforcement of laws of the Brčko District of BiH in the field of health,
- supervision over the legality of the work of health institutions in the Brčko District of BiH,
- Adoption of plans and programs of health care measures,
- creating a health activity development program,
- Inter-entity and international cooperation in the field of health care,
- Improvement of the health care quality system,
- Planning, monitoring and financing of health care in accordance with special regulations,
- Planning, development and realization of the capital investment program in investments in the healthcare sector,
- Drawing up a plan for the network of health institutions and organizations of the health system,
- The healthiness of water, foodstuffs and items of general use,
- social assistance and protection of citizens,
- Veterans' issues, war invalids and civilian victims of war,

- Other tasks within the competence of the Department of Health and other services determined by law and other regulations.

The Brčko District Health Insurance Fund provides mandatory health insurance and finances healthcare services for insured individuals within the district territory.

Comparative Analysis of Health Systems in Bosnia and Herzegovina

Aspect	FBiH	RS	Brčko District
Governance Structure	Decentralized; governed by ten cantonal ministries and the Federal Ministry of Health	Centralized; governed by the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare	Autonomous; governed by the Department of Health
Health Insurance Fund	Multiple funds (one for each canton + Federal fund)	Single health insurance fund	Single health insurance fund
Insurance Coverage (2020)	87% overall; varies by canton (84% - 100%)	74% of the population covered	High coverage; specifics depend on local regulations
Healthcare Levels	Organized into primary, secondary, and tertiary levels	Organized into primary, secondary, and tertiary levels	Organized across primary, secondary, and tertiary levels
Public vs. Private Facilities	Majority public, with growing private sector	Majority public, some private	Primarily public, limited private facilities

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3. Livestock sector and Veterinary Services Infrastructure in Bosnia and Herzegovina

The livestock sector in (BiH) is an integral part of the country's agriculture, featuring diverse livestock such as cattle, sheep, goats, pigs, and poultry. Livestock production contributes approximately 37% to the total value of agriculture in BiH, which is relatively low compared to countries with more developed agricultural sectors [21].

As of 2016, livestock statistics reported 455,000 cattle, 545,000 pigs, 1,016,000 sheep, and 20,290,000 poultry. The breeding livestock numbers included about 276,000 cows and heifers, 74,000 sows and gilts, and 593,000 yearling and breeding ewes [21]. Dairy production is a key agricultural sector, with approximately 13,000 to 14,000 agricultural holdings producing milk for the market [21].

In 2016, raw milk production was 701 million liters, with raw cow's milk accounting for about 97% of the total. Meat production has experienced a decline over the past decade across all categories. In 2016, net meat production totaled 85,000 tons, with poultry accounting for about 50% of this production, beef 30%, pork 15%, sheep 2%, and the remainder comprising other cattle and poultry meats [21].

Cattle farming is practiced year-round, with animals reared in stables or on pastures depending on the region. The predominant cattle breeds are Simmental (estimated at 80%), Holstein-Friesian (10%), and Brown Swiss (5%). Dairy farming is predominantly practiced in lowland and hilly areas with soils and climate suitable for higher yields of roughage [21].

Administrative organization and governance of Veterinary Services

Country level

The Veterinary Office of BiH, established under direct jurisdiction of the Ministry of Foreign Trade and Economic Relations of BiH (MFTER B&H) executes the legally set jurisdictions and in accordance with the operative activities of the entity veterinary services, as well as in accordance with the activities of the veterinary service of Brčko District. The Veterinary Office carries out the following activities:

- Proposes regulations and co-ordinates the execution of the peculiar measures, methods and control procedures for the infective and parasite diseases of the A and B lists of the international zoo-sanitary codex of the OIE;
- Proposes veterinary conditions for the international traffic (export from BiH and import to BiH) of animals, raw materials, litter and products of animal origin;
- Proposes conditions for registration of the animal slaughter facilities and execution of the peculiar procedure of registration of facilities for production, processing, tooling, finishing or keeping the products or raw materials of animal origin intended for export and import, respectively;
- Proposes regulations for the execution of a unique program of monitoring and control of the animal residuum, as well as for the products and raw materials of animal origin;
- Co-ordinates the work of the border veterinary inspection and proposes regulations for the settlement of the unique documentation for export and import, respectively, of animals, raw

materials, litter, and products of animal origin, as well as establishment of the unique information system of the border veterinary inspection;

- Co-operates with international veterinary, health and similar institutions and associations (WHO, WHO, FAO, European Commission, etc.).

Figure.4 – Organizational scheme of veterinary services in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Source) [22]

Veterinary services in Federation of Bosnia Herzegovina

Veterinary services in the (FBiH) are structured across multiple administrative levels, reflecting a decentralized governance model.

At the state level, the Veterinary Office of Bosnia and Herzegovina (VO BiH) serves as the central coordinating body under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Foreign Trade and Economic Relations. The VO BiH is responsible for coordinating entity veterinary services, drafting regulations, implementing uniform disease control measures, and supervising the epidemiological situation. At the entity level, the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Water Management, and Forestry oversees veterinary services in FBiH.

The FBiH is divided into 10 cantons, each with its own government and administrative structures. At the cantonal level, there are veterinary sectors within the cantonal ministries of agriculture. These cantonal veterinary services are responsible for implementing animal health and production programs within their jurisdictions. The cantonal veterinary inspection bodies work in cooperation with the entity-level veterinary inspectorates. In FBiH, there are four federal and 56 cantonal veterinary inspectors [23].

The reporting system in FBiH is hierarchical. The competent veterinary authorities in FBiH are responsible for implementing disease control and food safety programs. They have the right to issue sub-law documents that are not covered by state legislation.

The State Veterinary Office (SVO) issues an annual "Decision on measures of control of infectious and parasitic diseases of animals and their implementation and financing," which guides animal health controls for diseases of national interest.

Key responsibilities of veterinary services in general include:

- **Animal Health Protection:** Ensuring the health and welfare of animals.
- **Epidemiological Investigations:** Conducting investigations into infectious and parasitic disease outbreaks.
- **Data Collection and Analysis:** Collecting and analyzing epidemiological data.
- **Emergency Response Planning:** Designing plans for especially dangerous infectious diseases.
- **Database Maintenance:** Establishing and maintaining animal disease and health status databases.
- **Annual Planning:** Designing annual plans for disease monitoring and control [24].

These responsibilities are consistent with the Veterinary Law of BiH, which outlines public and social activities related to animal health protection, veterinary prevention, and control of infectious diseases [24].

In conclusion, the veterinary services in the FBiH operate within a multi-tiered system, with responsibilities distributed across entity and cantonal levels.

Figure.5 –Organizational Structure of Veterinary Services in the FBiH (Source: Created by the author as per information available in [24]).

This figure 5 outlines the veterinary reporting structure in FBiH, showing the hierarchical flow of information and coordination in animal health surveillance and disease control.

- The organizational structure of veterinary services in the FBiH is hierarchical and multi-layered, ensuring effective governance, professional oversight, and service delivery from the state level down to the field level.
- At the top of the hierarchy, the Ministry of Foreign Trade and Economic Relations (MoFTER) and the SVO provide overall policy guidance, coordination, and harmonization with international standards for the entire country. While the SVO operates at the state level, the following structure pertains specifically to the FBiH entity.
- Within FBiH, the Government of the FBiH oversees the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Water Management and Forestry. This Ministry is the central authority responsible for veterinary policy, legislation, and administration within the entity.

The Ministry’s Veterinary Sector is subdivided into two main divisions:

- **The Animal Health Protection Division**, which focuses on animal health, disease control, and animal welfare.

- **The Public Health Division**, which addresses veterinary public health, food safety of animal origin, and hygiene standards.

Parallel to the Veterinary Sector, the Federal Administration for Inspection Affairs (FAIA) is responsible for the enforcement of veterinary legislation and inspection activities. The Veterinary Inspectorate of FBiH, operating under FAIA, supervises veterinary inspection and compliance across the entity. Below the federal level, the structure is further decentralized:

- Cantonal Ministries of Agriculture in each of the ten cantons have their own veterinary sectors and inspectorates, implementing federal policies and conducting inspections at the cantonal level.
- Cantonal Veterinary Inspectorates supervise and support Municipal Veterinary Inspectorates, which are established in larger municipalities and are responsible for local enforcement and reporting.

At the operational level, veterinary organizations including veterinary stations, clinics, and hospitals provide direct veterinary services to animal owners and farmers. These organizations are registered and monitored by the relevant authorities. Additionally, advisory and support institutions such as the Veterinary Chamber and the National Veterinary Institute play important roles in professional regulation, licensing, training, diagnostics, and laboratory support.

Veterinary services in Republic of Srpska

The Veterinary Service is a service of special interest to the RS in the area of combating infectious animal diseases and protecting the population from zoonoses, ensuring the safety and suitability of food of animal origin for humans, as well as other measures significant for public health.

The Veterinary Law in the RS ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Srpska", no. 75/17 and 63/24) regulates the conditions and manner of performing veterinary activities, animal health protection, detection, prevention of occurrence, control, and eradication of infectious animal diseases, prevention of diseases that are common to animals and humans, implementation of veterinary public health measures, veterinary health inspection of animal breeding and trade, animal products, animal feed, water, and animal by-products, animal reproduction, official control and inspection oversight in the field of veterinary medicine, animal marking, veterinary information system, operation of the veterinary chamber, professional development in the field of veterinary medicine, veterinary protection of the environment, and animal welfare.

Inspection oversight in accordance with this law and regulations adopted based on this law is performed by veterinary inspectors and food inspectors of the Republic Administration for Inspection Affairs and local self-government units within their competencies.

Administrative supervision over the implementation of this law and regulations adopted on its basis is performed by the Ministry Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Management.

Overall organizational infrastructure consists of:

- (1) Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Water Management of the RS, Veterinary Department

- (2) Veterinary Chamber
- (3) Veterinary Station
- (4) Veterinary Clinic
- (5) Republic Inspection within the Republic Administration for Inspection Affairs
- (6) Veterinary Inspection in local self-government units
- (7) Public Institution Veterinary Institute of the RS "Dr. Vaso Butozan" Banja Luka
- (8) Veterinary Laboratory "Slaven" *private
- (9) Veterinary Institute "Teolab" *private

Figure.6 – Organization of veterinary sector in Republic of Srpska as provided by RS authorities

The veterinary service of RS cooperates with the VO BiH which is under governance of the Ministry of Foreign Trade and Economic Relations of Bosnia and Herzegovina (MFTER B&H).

Figure.7 – Reporting scheme in veterinary sector of Republic of Srpska as provided by RS authorities

Veterinary services in Brčko District

Brčko District operates an independent healthcare system, separate from the entities of FBiH and RS [23].

Brčko District has its own veterinary inspectorate, which is responsible for implementing inspections related to health surveillance, food safety, application of standards in facilities, and movement of live animals and products of animal origin. The district participates in national animal disease control and eradication programs, which are issued and financed on an annual basis through the budgets of relevant institutions at central, regional, and local levels. Veterinary organizations in Brčko District implement primary health care, including vaccination and treatment of animals, and along with veterinary inspectors, form the first line of disease control.

The Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management in Brčko District has broadly the same roles as the entity Ministries of Agriculture, Water Management and Forestry [23]. Within this department, a sub-department deals with veterinary certification, veterinary checks on products, animal feed and water, farm waste, use of veterinary medicines, and controls on animal semen, ova and embryos. The sub-department also maintains registers of farms/animals on a regional and national level, monitors harmful substances/residues in food, and is responsible for the introduction and development of the information system in the veterinary sector [23].

This infrastructure allows Brčko District to manage its livestock sector and veterinary services independently while still coordinating with state-level institutions for overall animal health and disease control in BiH.

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4. Situational Analysis of One Health and Arbovirus in Bosnia and Herzegovina

The OH approach, which integrates human, animal, and environmental health, is crucial for addressing complex health issues. In BiH the FBiH, RS and Brčko District contribute to this approach. The current state of OH, zoonotic diseases, and arboviruses in BiH, as well as the broader Balkan region from 2010 to the present, was reviewed. The intersection of these topics is critical for understanding and mitigating zoonotic diseases in the region.

Search Strategy

To conduct this literature review, a comprehensive search was performed across PubMed and Google Scholar using the following search strings: "Bosnia and Herzegovina" AND "One Health" AND "arbovirus," "Bosnia and Herzegovina" AND "One Health," "Bosnia and Herzegovina" AND "One Health" AND "zoonotic disease," and "Bosnia and Herzegovina" AND "arbovirus." The review covered literature from 2010 to 2024, focusing on peer-reviewed articles, reports, and studies directly relevant to these topics. Studies not available in English or not directly relevant to One Health scope were excluded.

Key Insights from Literature on One Health in Bosnia and Herzegovina

The literature review revealed a limited number of studies directly addressing the intersection of OH, arboviruses, and zoonotic diseases in BiH and the Balkans.

- 1- OH Awareness and implementation:** a survey on OH perception and implementation was conducted in the 37 countries involved in the European Project COST, including BiH, highlighting the current state of OH initiatives. The survey revealed that while awareness of OH is relatively high among EU countries, a comprehensive understanding of the concept is limited. Key issues identified were antimicrobial resistance, avian influenza, and environmental pollution. Challenges such as poor intersectoral communication and differing priorities hinder effective collaboration. BiH met the expected respondent rate, indicating interest in participation in OH initiatives. The study recommends improving communication and understanding between sectors to enhance OH implementation [25].
- 2- Cystic Echinococcosis (CE):** in BiH a retrospective study was conducted on cystic echinococcosis between 2016 and 2020, examining its prevalence in both human and sheep populations. The study found 44 cases in humans and established a significant correlation between the number of sheep and the incidence of the disease in humans. These findings underscore the importance of an integrated approach to disease control, consistent with the OH concept, which advocates for collaborative efforts across human, animal, and environmental health sectors to improve health outcomes and disease prevention. In FBiH, 83 infectious diseases, including echinococcosis, are mandatory for reporting, and until now, in FBiH, out of all clinical manifestations, only CE is documented [26].
- 3- Parasitic Infections in Wildlife:** in BiH a study investigated parasitic infections in wildlife, focusing on zoonotic parasites that pose risks to both animal and human health. The research included various wildlife species such as bears, red foxes, wolves, wildcats, badgers, martens, wild boars, deer, and hares. Significant zoonotic parasites identified were *Toxocara canis*, *Uncinaria* spp., *Trichinella* spp., and *Echinococcus* spp. While the study did not explicitly adopt a OH approach, its findings underscore the interconnected health of wildlife, domestic animals,

and humans, emphasizing the necessity for integrated management to mitigate zoonotic disease risks [27].

- 4- **Anthrax in BiH:** in the past 25 years, BiH has experienced sporadic anthrax cases in ruminants. Notably, in September 2014, two men contracted cutaneous anthrax from handling an infected cow carcass, highlighting the zoonotic risk. The most recent case was reported in 2017. Environmental changes, potentially influenced by climate change, can activate dormant *Bacillus anthracis* spores, posing a continuous threat. A OH approach, integrating human, animal, and environmental health strategies, is essential for effective monitoring and control. Preventive measures such as livestock vaccination, movement restrictions, and proper carcass disposal are crucial [28].
- 5- **Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever Virus (CCHFV) in BiH:** a 2022 study reported the first evidence of CCHFV circulation in BiH. Researchers tested 176 sheep from Gacko and Nevesinje and found CCHFV-specific antibodies in 9.66% of the samples, confirming virus circulation in the region. The study emphasizes the need for integrated surveillance and control measures to prevent the spread of this tick-borne zoonosis [29].
- 6- **Cryptosporidium and Giardia Surveillance:** in a comprehensive review of *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* in Eastern Europe, data from BiH reveal that while these parasites are present in humans and animals, the lack of mandatory reporting and inconsistent diagnostic methods hamper effective monitoring and control. Research from the University of Sarajevo indicates these pathogens' presence in human stool samples. To improve public health outcomes, the review recommends standardizing diagnostic and reporting practices across the region [30].
- 7- **Leptospirosis:** as an emerging zoonosis, is widespread globally and is of significant concern due to its zoonotic potential. Research in BiH has revealed seroprevalence rates in dogs [31,32,33,34] and foxes [33] confirming the role of canids in the spread of leptospirosis. Additionally, studies have highlighted the impact of climate change, including heavy rainfall and flooding, on the seroprevalence of leptospirosis [33]. Effective prevention and control of the disease require a comprehensive approach that includes monitoring and controlling seroprevalence, as well as adapting prevention strategies in line with climate changes and the disease's ecology.
- 8- **Trichinellosis:** a retrospective study analyzes incidence of trichinellosis in BiH over 61 years, highlighting the influence of social, economic, political, and cultural factors on the disease's spread. It underscores the need for mandatory meat inspection for *Trichinella spp.* larvae due to significant regional differences in infection rates and the impact of various factors, including biosecurity and public awareness [35]. Molecular epidemiology finds both *Trichinella pseudospiralis* and *T. spiralis* were identified in a domestic pig, with *T. pseudospiralis* being a rare find. Additionally, *T. britovi* was detected in a wild boar, and *Trichinella britovi* in red foxes [36].
- 9- **CCHF Surveillance in Ticks and Cattle:** A 2022 study provided the first combined molecular and serologic evidence of CCHFV circulation in BiH, confirming its endemic presence. CCHFV RNA was detected in *Hyalomma marginatum* ticks, and 14.97% of tested cattle had CCHFV antibodies, with the highest prevalence in Eastern Herzegovina. These findings highlight the need for integrated vector surveillance and OH based approaches to monitor and manage zoonotic risks in the region [37].
- 10- **Avian Influenza Surveillance and Molecular Characterization:** A 2023 study reported the detection and whole genome sequencing of highly pathogenic avian influenza A (H5N1) virus, clade 2.3.4.4b, in a mute swan found in northern BiH. Conducted under the national surveillance program, the study confirmed genetic similarity with strains from neighboring countries, suggesting potential cross-border spread via wild birds. The findings highlight the importance of molecular surveillance and wildlife monitoring in early detection of zoonotic threats and support the integration of virological data into national OH preparedness efforts [38].

- 11- Surveillance of Tick-Borne Pathogens in *Dermacentor reticulatus*:** A 2024 study investigated zoonotic pathogens in *Dermacentor reticulatus* ticks collected from animals and vegetation across BiH. The study confirmed the presence of *Rickettsia* spp., *Babesia* spp. reported for the first time in this tick species in BiH. Given the presence of multiple pathogens of public health relevance and the expanding geographic and host range of *D. reticulatus*, the study underscores the urgent need to establish a national tick and tick-borne disease surveillance system [39].
- 12- Tick-Borne Pathogen Surveillance in *Ixodes* Ticks:** A large-scale surveillance study conducted between 2017 and 2023 investigated the presence of zoonotic pathogens in *Ixodes ricinus* ticks across various ecological zones and host species in BiH. The study confirmed the presence of *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*, *Rickettsia* spp., *Borrelia burgdorferi* s.l., and *Babesia* spp., with some samples showing co-infections. These findings contribute essential baseline data for assessing tick-borne disease risk and highlight the epidemiological relevance of *I. ricinus* in the region. The study reinforces the need for a national tick surveillance system and supports a OH approach to vector-borne disease monitoring by integrating wildlife, veterinary, and environmental health perspectives [40].
- 13- Human-to-Pet Transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in BiH:** A 2022 study provided the first molecular evidence of SARS-CoV-2 transmission from humans to companion animals in household settings in BiH. Swab samples collected from pets (primarily dogs and cats) living with COVID-19 positive individuals were tested, and the detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA confirmed the risk of reverse zoonosis. These findings emphasize the role of pets as potential incidental hosts and highlight the importance of including companion animals in OH surveillance frameworks during pandemics. The study reinforces the need for multisectoral collaboration to better understand virus transmission dynamics at the human-animal interface and to inform public health strategies [41].
- 14- Lloviu Virus Identified in Schreiber’s Bats in BiH:** A 2023 study employed metagenomic sequencing on tissue samples from dead Schreiber’s bats and confirmed the presence of Lloviu virus (LLOV) in BiH for the first time. LLOV, a filovirus related to Ebola and Marburg viruses, has been associated with bat die-offs in Europe and is considered a potential emerging zoonotic threat. This detection expands the known geographic distribution of the virus and underscores the importance of genomic tools in identifying high-consequence pathogens in wildlife. The study reinforces the need for active wildlife pathogen surveillance and integrated genomic monitoring within a broader OH approach to emerging infectious disease preparedness in the region [42].
- 15- Ten-Year Surveillance of *Trichinella* in Carnivores in BiH:** A 2024 study analyzed ten years (2013–2023) of surveillance data on *Trichinella* spp. in wild and domestic carnivores across BiH. *Trichinella* larvae were detected in multiple samples, with *T. britovi* as the most prevalent species, followed by *T. spiralis* and *T. pseudospiralis*. The results highlight the ongoing circulation of *Trichinella* spp. in wildlife and the need to integrate long-term monitoring into national control efforts. This study supports a OH approach to managing zoonotic risks at the animal-human-environment interface [43].

OH Initiatives in BiH

BiH has been actively involved in the MediLabSecure (MLS) project, which aims to strengthen capacity and networking activities in the field of vector knowledge and mosquito-borne diseases. As one of the beneficiary countries since 2014, BiH has had opportunities to enhance its capabilities in areas such as integrated surveillance of vector-borne diseases, risk assessment for emerging arboviruses, and laboratory diagnostics for viral pathogens [44]. The Faculty of Veterinary Medicine at the University of Sarajevo is listed as an implementer for the MediLabSecure project in BiH. This

involvement has promoted the adoption of the OH approach, fostering collaboration between public health, veterinary health, and entomology sectors in the country [44]. The project has facilitated knowledge sharing and collaboration with other countries in the Mediterranean and Black Sea regions, contributing to improving BiH's preparedness for common health threats at both national and regional levels [44].

The University of Sarajevo offers an interdisciplinary master program based on the OH concept. This program aims to expand competencies in recognizing, analyzing, and containing health disorders in human and animal populations [45].

BiH is part of the Balkans OH Network ([Balkan One Health Network \(bohnetwork.org\)](http://bohnetwork.org)).

Gaps and Limitation

There is a notable scarcity of comprehensive data specifically addressing the OH approach and arbovirus infections in BiH. The following gaps were identified:

Limited Publications

- There is a dearth of peer-reviewed articles and systematic studies focusing on the implementation and outcomes of OH initiatives in BiH.

Fragmented Health System: The complex and fragmented health system in BiH poses challenges for cohesive implementation of OH strategies.

Resource Allocation: BiH face significant challenges in efficient resource allocation across various sectors, including health. Inefficient allocation of resources and insufficient investment hinder the country's ability to address critical issues such as zoonotic diseases and public health. Additionally, the highly decentralized governance structure exacerbates these inefficiencies, affecting the quality of public services, particularly in health and education sectors [46,47,48].

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